

FUNCTIONAL APPROACH TO THE STUDY OF MORPHOLOGY IN ELEMENTARY SCHOOL.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7489864>

ELSEVIER

Received: 22-12-2022

Accepted: 22-12-2022

Published: 22-12-2022

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Abstract: The article discusses the functional approach to the study of morphology in elementary school and the knowledge, skills, and abilities provided in the consistent course of the mother tongue, the purpose of the mother tongue lessons, including the methods of teaching nouns in general schools. The teaching process of 'lib' and 'noun' vocabulary is explained through practical tasks and examples in a series.

Keywords: word groups, noun group, morphology, assignment, mother tongue, student, school.

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INTRODUCTION

The Uzbek language, one of the oldest and richest languages in the world, is national for our people, it is a symbol of our identity and independent statehood, an invaluable spiritual wealth, a great value. The mother of our language is the state and also the society in his life the effect and also the office more increase, Improvement of the law "On the state language" in view of today's requirements is necessary.

Mother language classes the purpose of students to increase literacy, speech skills to grow, creative thinking orientation with one in line with the mother of our language is to maintain purity.

MAIN PART

It is known that education in the system of all sciences, especially the Uzbek language in their classrooms is too didactic materials, game exercises, visual teaching aids to use a good result for ladies. This is about a series of experts, including such linguists as R. Ishmukhamedov, A. Nisanbayeva, B. Tokhliev, K. Usmonova who thought in scientific papers, monographs and articles. Mother language in their classrooms word category topics, especially the horse word category in teaching grammar assignments, should be shown tools, the distribution of materials to use through the students' skill as well as the skills and abilities of the harvest to make didactic means of education in the process of place, For him, special features analysis to do effective results obtained

gives students to the morphology of the original data with the original in the classes they get to know each other. Horse words, adjectives, numbers, verbs,

pronouns, helper They have been able to classify words into groups since elementary school. Permanent mother tongue from the course to be provided knowledge, qualifications, skills and abilities above all initial in the classes employed knowledge, qualifications as well as logic skills continues.

I also teach morphology at the school of scientific and practical necessity. Its scientific necessity is the Syntax section, which will be studied in the next step. directly related to morphology. Because the convention of possession and also the person-number complement although the morphology of the object despite the fact that however they have to talk in the design of the word and also the connection word between the syntactic contact provider tool is considered. The additional speaking syntax of learning directly to the word assistant that Morphology performs is even more important given its relevance to the tasks. earns. [2.54].

Thus, the school course of morphology solves the following tasks. holds in the eye:

- pupils word do words new forms crop do teach; the word reserve increase, from the word Correctly and also the appropriate use of the qualification extension;
- words relation from forms to use qualification extension;
- scientific literacy improvement;
- talk group and text Create job qualifications;
- in DTS in the eye caught requirements based on each one subject training in the process of it with the sequence Fulfilled to increase

The teacher gives the students a group of words. On the topic, I learned to repeat the knowledge of the dictionary under dictation possible

Dictionary dictation

House, wedding, stone, lightning, thunder, tree, meeting, manners, pain, friendship, book, worker, handsome, small, cute, educated, white, read, write, sew, come, think, worked, slept, talked spoke .

I write the dictation after the students each one word explanatory dictionary meaning Comments and also its which word categories dependent on what they say should be 1 - assignment.

1. House - people life window, door, roof is construction: house - what? To the question answer noun this word belongs to the category

2. Wedding is a celebration cradle wedding wedding wedding circumcision wedding gold wedding such as a grand ceremony; wedding - what? the horse will answer the question to the group of words included.

3. Worker - something useful Work with a worker person; who? the horse will answer the question

4. Beautiful - synonyms: beautiful, beautiful, attractive; as? the question will be answered qualitatively.

5. studied worked - completed movement meaning: interested in reading without stopping worked verb

29 - task. Make up phrases and sentences with these words. Who? which? as? what did he do what does it mean words that are answers to questions to the bottom draw them like a word in a series dependent saying this give

3. horse, qualitative, category verb about words separate group.

That's all the way the explanatory dictionary dictation contains the words of the oral comment, the students:

- Thinking scope expands;
- thought expressing skill develops;
- in speech the word apply qualification is formed;
- The word category on the surface of busy knowledge is summarized.

One of the independent groups of words is the group of nouns. The subject of the noun Who is the name? which? be the answer to questions, I write nouns with a capital letter, to horses to be added the agreement of the addition of the original from the classes to the students is known. It is the word turkumini in the process of learning first of all the mother It is the scientists in the memory of the restoration so that again the commemoration and also partly to creativity on the basis of educational exercises will be carried out. Repetition in the process of "thing" is necessary to dwell more broadly on the concept. The theme implies not only manual work, the eye to see or the measure of what was possible was a thing, perhaps a community of expressive names (food, construction), nature Events as well as other events name (flood, earthquake, thunder), noun actions (knowledge, skin), nouns of the sign state (stinginess, generosity, freedom, anxiety) are also understood.

Necessary in relation to the lexical eaning, morphological features and syntactic functions of the noun knowledge, qualifications as well as skills and abilities, mostly practical work through the students in his opinion is absorbed. Challenge students with these vocabulary words as required by the program. lexical forms (numeral form, diminutive forms) proper nouns and related nouns, proper nouns, their types and spelling, personal names, toponyms (toponyms) and their spelling, product names and spelling; soul mate of a horse as well as their groups (obviously as well as abstract nouns, semantic groups of concrete nouns, personal nouns, related nouns, to the profession according to the horse man, man is another aspect according to the horse arrows, the man of the connection with nouns, animal names (zoonyms), names of trees and plants, objects fathers, material, raw value of the horse, place (space) of the horse, moment (time) value of the horse, Annotation of the horse on the surface of the necessary knowledge, qualifications, as well as skills and abilities with weapons in sight caught.

The study of the group of words "horse" with general information about this group begins. Pupils Tashkent, Bukhara, "Bud", "Uzbekistan the voice of Rozimurodov, flower, song, bread and salt, beauty, health, art, sophistication as horses each to one question to give as well as independent groups Continue to continue each one in the horse group for the overall value determination and also commentary through the original in the classes occupied knowledge in memory recovery and also its strengthening the possibility will have This independent thing to carry out as a result they have the following to

the conclusion will come:

Who? Which? The answer to the questions one person, the names of things, one type of noun is included in the series. [3.101].

After that, the topic "Lexical forms of nouns" will be studied. Pupils of horses the number of forms to learn they have trees, at home how to work on the form of words, other means of expressing the meaning of the plural to identify; adverbs that form sentences with the participation of these words and express the plural meaning they comment on.

How nouns are studied, first of all, in words that are included in sentences with nouns. work to take Let's go For example given words: 1) people Name, family nouns representing a nickname; 2) geographical names; 3) various organizations, enterprises, institutions names; 4) names of planets and stars; 5) historical events, diary, window and scientific institutions names; 6) to animals special placed names such as in the separation group, the crop was independent Continue to continue "sign name-compound place names in the form of" related noun ", geographical names in the form of" noun with the name of the feature " list make-up, put up as a creative and practical cases of students writing literacy increase as well as the word is important to expand the reserve is important.

A person from the text to enrich the vocabulary of teachers with personal nouns to distinguish between nouns, group them by roots and forms, give meaning to individual words and expand groups by choosing nested words, -chi, -vchi, -uvchi, -dosh, -kor, -zor, - the formation of personal nouns with the help of suffixes, such as shunos, a dictionary of double personal nouns make-up, putting up their spelling at work such as a creative and practical task is ready. Based on the knowledge gained by students, asking questions about nouns from any text, they are determined after reaching the horse of the subject accuracy, that is, work, see They are divided into concrete and abstract, depending on whether they are measurable or not. as well as the harvest was an independent group Continue They do For example: Work, look, you can measure the objects name In addition, work, look, you can measure not happened items name also bus factory worker product

- what kind

-- courtesy extravagance flow feeling - like

- Like

Working on compound nouns is important for expanding students' vocabulary. happening. The extraction of nominal phrases from the text occurs in the presence of given words creative and practical work, such as creating compounds of such compounds with in enrichment important important especially, this chapter or subordinate to the word the words. For example, students of our school like speeches, victories, weddings, boyfriends, girlfriends. words found adding Our school library, Our daughter's school such as the word education links they do.

One of the most difficult problems for students is joint nouns and their spelling. This is a place from the vocabulary given

in the study of the topic forming names (black lake robber, new husband, junior, seven sons-seven sons, old machit-konamachit, big fortress-Kattakurgan vh) compound words word turning into compounds (cotton flower-cotton flower , headache-headache, physical education-body education, ice-cream-ice ice cream, flower market-flower market, horse market market vh) given compound words explanatory dictionary make-up, put up their writing comment as a creative-practical task to use this subject thorough master provides.

Consolidating the acquired knowledge about nouns, their methodology uses texts on various topics in a teaching manner to develop in relation to the will Noun learned in the course of earlier forays into text analysis category about Information rely.

With this, the next practical task is ready.

1 - appointment. Explain the dictionary meaning of the nouns found in the text. how to answer a question to be tell me

2 - toshirik Divided to words meaningful and also a neighbor in the nest of the word to choose

3 - appointment. Who? which? where? Which words are the answers to the questions to say that it belongs to the series. With them, word forms noun+noun, adjective+noun, number+noun form combinations.

4. Vintage Done the word compound in the presence of the phrase make-up, put up

5. Special phrases specific to the topic in the presence of the text Create

Mother language training mother so the development of the study of the task, Carrying out through exercises and text simulations is the basis for a systematic and consistent learning. prepares, improves the content of training, accelerates educational and cognitive activity. The theory is exercised on the ground teaching independent thinking as well as creative ability to grow helping ladies.

Students learn derivational, inflectional and formative adverbs. especially necessary knowledge, qualifications and skills and abilities after acquiring the word composition with they get to know each other as well as the words basis especially the generalization of the harvest they do.

This word category carefully study is the foundation.

Mother language training in the pupil oral as well as written speech perfectly adopt the language of the possibilities Properly and also fruitfully use the culture teaches. Speech culture is simply from a greeting pulling to whom, Why when, where how to speak, oriental secrets of manners teaches. [4.63].

Morphology teaching the student independent as well as creative thinking sphere expands, different forms of the word are appropriate in the structure of the sentence and in coherent speech use skills and abilities develop.

CONCLUSION

Uzbek in the language of the word category learning source in the classroom studied on the basis of knowledge, repetition, strengthening and generalization for the following using questions possible

1. Uzbek language word categories how are the groups divided?
2. Independent category word which
3. Horse word category classification do it
4. Independent category word definition give
5. Does the word category assistant independent word from the categories like the other one?
6. words to categories in separation which Features attention taken?

Whether the reader is able to correctly classify the words in the text into groups of sentences in the definition does not suffer too much. So, it's parsing itself with parsing will be connected. Syntactic analysis without a full understanding of the meaning of groups of words words that do not enter into a grammatical relationship with the main members of the sentence Identification (pcs.). possible it is not.

The analysis of phrases, as well as the analysis of phrases, morphological analysis of one appearance, the existence of a school in the program "Word Categories" questions on the topic cover takes

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